

The Blue Climate Initiative

Solutions for People, Ocean, Planet

Why the Ocean?

The ocean sustains life on Earth. It feeds and protects us. It delights and astounds us. It is at once a vital resource and an incalculable part of our natural world. The ocean generates an astounding half of the world's oxygen while also absorbing a quarter of Earth's carbon dioxide emissions. Over three billion people depend on the ocean for their primary source of nutrition. A healthy ocean has an estimated net asset value of US\$ 24 trillion.¹

Yet the ocean is also under threat. As it suffers, so does its ability to sustain and protect humanity. Whether from the effects of global warming, pollution, or extractive activities, ocean health is diminishing, and the extraordinary biodiversity that it supports is disappearing. Indeed, declining ocean health could cost the global economy more than US\$ 400 billion annually by 2050.² The most catastrophic of these reinforcing feedback loops is the rising concentration of carbon dioxide in our atmosphere resulting in accelerating climate change and ocean acidification. The clarion call from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) could not be more stark: we now have less than ten years left to dramatically reset the course toward a 1.5°C future.

The global community is increasingly realizing the ocean's extraordinary power, as well as its vulnerability. None too soon. There is still time to reverse direction. If responsibly protected, restored, and managed, oceans could reverse the buildup of carbon in our atmosphere while also sustainably supplying humanity with abundant energy, fresh water, nutritious food, improved health, and economic opportunity for those who depend on the blue economy. To unlock these urgently needed solutions, we need immediate concerted action - an ocean innovation movement.

The Blue Climate Initiative

The Blue Climate Initiative accelerates ocean-related strategies to address the climate crisis, focusing on three impact areas:

- People - Resilient, thriving and equitable communities
- Ocean - An understood and protected ocean
- Planet - A restored and healthy climate

We convene scientists, community groups, engineers, entrepreneurs, investors, government leaders and influencers to protect the ocean and use its remarkable power to tackle climate change and other urgent issues of our time, from renewable energy and sustainable food supplies to human health and resilient ocean economies. Through a holistic approach and

¹ High Level Panel for a Sustainable Ocean Economy: <https://www.oceanpanel.org/about-the-ocean>

² *Ibid.*

cross-sector collaboration, we pursue seven strategic objectives to advance collective attention and investment:

- *Enhanced collaboration* around ocean-based solutions through network platforms and data infrastructure;
- *Deepened inclusive scientific understanding* of the ocean, including the ocean’s role as a solution to climate change;
- *Expanded blue innovation* including new technologies, models, and ideas that provide impactful solutions;
- *Increased financing for a blue economy*, with emphasis on sustainability and equity;
- *Strengthened policy* that better protects the ocean against pollution, biodiversity loss, and other threats, and that further enables ocean and climate action;
- *Changed behavior* among consumers and industry towards more ocean- and climate-conscious action and decision-making; and
- *Informed, engaged, and empowered citizens and communities.*

The BCI is guided by the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals -- particularly #13 (Climate Action) and #14 (Life Below Water), alongside #1 (No Poverty), #2 (Zero Hunger), #3 (Good Health and Well-Being) and #7 (Affordable & Clean Energy). We achieve our work through #17 (Partnerships for the Goals). The BCI also aligns with the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, which envisions “the science we need for the ocean we want” and encourages “transformative ocean science solutions for sustainable development, connecting people and our ocean”.

Transformational Opportunities for People, Ocean and Planet

In early 2020 the BCI asked a question. What would we do if we had a billion dollars to direct toward the most innovative, impactful solutions to climate change, using the power of the ocean? To answer this question we asked sixty world-class experts from across the globe to identify the most promising options -- which we called Transformational Opportunities (TOPS) -- at the intersection of the ocean, climate change, and humanity's well-being. They collaborated in working groups across six thematic areas: Health and Well-Being, Food and Nutrition, Marine Energy and Transportation, Mineral and Genetic Resources, Biodiversity and Nature-Based Solutions, and Sustainable Tourism. They considered multiple pathways, including technological innovation, policy change, community organization and public outreach, and each had specific, viable recommendations for action.

The BCI's collaborators identified over forty Transformational Opportunities that can sustain our people, steward our ocean, and heal our planet:

Transformational Opportunities for People, Ocean and Planet

Turning Ideas into Action: 2021 Priorities

These Transformational Opportunities, presented in a forthcoming Compendium and six standalone papers, are the “evidence base” for our action agenda. The BCI has now entered a new phase -- *Turning Ideas into Action* -- with a focus on the following priorities in 2021:

1. **Support and fund concrete action through incentive prizes**, especially through:
 - a. *Community Prize* - Support winners across six communities in South-East Asia, Polynesia, Micronesia, East Africa, the Caribbean and South America
 - b. *Innovation Prize* - Launch, run and award a prize for entrepreneurs, supporting market-based innovation that addresses climate change mitigation through human-centered, ocean-related solutions based in sound science
2. **Advance the ocean agenda through strategic collective action initiatives**, e.g:
 - a. *Healthy Blue Communities Network* - Scope and pilot an interconnected global web of coastal and island communities, working on ocean, natural, social, economic and political sciences, to develop and share ocean-based solutions
 - b. *Tetiaroa / Moorea pilot projects* - Serve as a living laboratory such as for a marine permaculture farm using deep-ocean water upwelling
 - c. *Opportunistic collaboration* - Using emergent strategy, support BCI's collaborators as needs and windows of opportunity arise, eg on seabed mining, the Blue New Deal, and the decade of deep ocean exploration and research
3. **Enhance awareness of key ocean issues through media and communication:**
 - a. Create media and raise awareness to influence perception and behaviors on key issues at the ocean/climate nexus
4. **Advance the ocean solutions evidence base through TOPS paper publication:**
 - a. Publish and disseminate the Transformational Opportunities Compendium and standalone papers to provoke interest and action
5. **Build momentum toward a first Blue Climate Summit:**
 - a. Advance planning for a 300+ person action-oriented event to be hosted in French Polynesia, likely in early 2022, to showcase solutions, disseminate knowledge, and accelerate momentum by matching funders and solution providers

BCI's Governance and Sponsorship

The BCI is governed by a Steering Committee, under expansion into a full Board chaired by the BCI's CEO and engaging Co-convenors or their representatives. A subset of members will comprise an Executive Committee, informed by Special Advisors. Additional stakeholder groups provide expertise and links to action: 60+ thematic experts who co-authored the TOPS, judges for the BCI prizes; community and NGO representatives that influence BCI decisions; entrepreneurs engaged through challenges and initiatives. The program is implemented by a lean Core Team driving day-to-day operations management, administration and finance, stakeholder liaison and partnerships, incentive prizes, fundraising, communications and Summit preparation.

The BCI's fiscal sponsor to date is the Tetiaroa Society, a 501(c)(3) nonprofit organization (tetiaroasociety.org). The BCI is actively welcoming additional sponsors to expand its impact.